

Western Land Services Pty Ltd

Surbiton Park Weed Management Plan

Planning for Action

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Vegetation Management Plan: Werribee River, Surbiton Park

1. INTRODUCTION

Western Land Services was engaged by Western Water to undertake a vegetation survey and prepare a Vegetation Management Plan (VMP) for a 2.5 km stretch of the Werribee River in Melton South, Victoria.

A field survey of Surbiton Park, Werribee River in the Werribee River catchment was undertaken on 16th July 2013. Field data was collected for 35 priority environmental weeds that occur within the riparian to escarpment area. Condition of the vegetation was also noted.

The purpose of this survey was to collect simple data on priority weeds, including their location, extent and impact. A second component was to adequately plan the activity effort of weed control and projected environmental weed cover abundance. This Vegetation Management Plan will be used to implement environmental works for the enhancement of existing habitat within the Park.

2 Study Area

The Werribee River lies in the Werribee River catchment approximately 34 kilometres west of Melbourne.

The project zone (study area) is approximately 2.5 km in length and comprises the riparian corridor of Werribee River (Surbiton Park) on left sides to top of the escarpment. The upstream extent of the project zone is bounded by Griegs Road, Melton South, and the downstream boundary is a fence line at the end of Stage 2 within the Park. Land within the study area is a mix of forested stream banks, grassy slopes and rocky escarpments with woodland species. Land use is passive grazing / conservation.

The site is managed jointly by Western Water

For Practicality and ease of access to the site the study area has been divided into seven reaches, defined by local term of reference and physical features (Table 1 and Figure 1).

Table 1: Description of the reaches surveyed within the Crown Reserve

Sub reach Number	Reach Description	Landuse	Land Ownership	Length
1	Wallaby Gully- Griegs Rd to Werribee River confluence	Grazing / conservation	Western Water	437 m
2	Werribee River confluence downstream to first fence	Grazing / conservation	Western Water	262 m
3	First fence downstream to Thistle Flat	Grazing / conservation	Western Water	307 m
4	Thistle Flat downstream to Poa Slope	Grazing / conservation	Western Water	228 m
5	Poa Slope downstream to Access track	Grazing / conservation	Western Water	206 m
6	A Class Gully	Grazing / conservation	Western Water	270 m
7	A Class Gully confluence to end of Stage 3	Grazing / conservation	Western Water	598 m

Figure 1: Aerial photograph of entire project zone and sub reach locations.

3 Desktop Assessment

The Victorian Biodiversity Atlas (VBA 2007) was reviewed to identify the weed species known to occur within 5 kilometres of the Park. The search identified 24 exotic species, including species listed as Weeds of National Significance (WoNS)

A survey was undertaken on 16th July to identify high priority weeds within the Park. The control methodology and treatment efforts were noted. This data was captured manually and then transcribed into a Vegetation Assessment Worksheet (Table 3).

Weeds that were observed to have minimal impact on habitat in the context of this report, such as *Cirsium vulgare* (Spear Thistle), *Hypochoeris radicata* (Flatweed), *Ehrharta erecta* (Panic Velt), *Poa annua* (Winter Grass), were not recorded. This term was applied mostly to small terrestrial species not considered by peer opinion to represent a clear and present threat to the natural values of the general location and study area.

In order to identify the cover and abundance of each weed infestation, a visual assessment of density was undertaken. A visual assessment is the simplest way to determine weed density, and although this method can be subjective, it is considered appropriate for the requirements of this report. The Braun-Blanquet scale of cover abundance was used to quantify each weed species and recorded as a percentage. This approach was applied to weeds found within the study area.

Table 3: Data collected for Vegetation Assessment Worksheet

Scientific Name	Common Name	Conservation Status	Cover Abundance	DSE Advisory List / weed rating	WONS	CaLP
		Listed,	"r, +, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5"	1–30 Very High Risk Weeds	Y OR N	Y OR N
		Vulnerable		31–60 High Risk Weeds		
		Rare		61–90 Moderately High Risk Weeds		
				91–120 Medium Risk Weeds		
				121–243 Lower Risk Weeds		

The noxious status of recorded weeds under the Victorian Catchment and Land Protection Act 1994 (CaLP Act) was determined and their rankings on the DSE Advisory list of environmental weeds of the Ranges Bioregions of Victoria (Adair *et al.*, 2008) were determined by desktop review and noted.

The DSE Advisory list of environmental weeds is a non-statutory classification system that ranks environmental weeds on a basis of five attributes: Potential for invasion; impact on natural systems; area of potential distribution; range of susceptible habitat; and rate of dispersal (Adair *et al.*, 2008). Its purpose is to provide an indication of the level of risk posed by individual species within a defined bioregion. The advisory list, in combined with observations made in the field and the author's

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knowledge of weed ecology, was used to assign *invasiveness*, *impact*, and *control* categories to the recorded weeds.

Overall, the nomination of a given species' control methodology and effort of treatment was based on:

- the abundance of the species,
- the patch size,
- quality of the adjacent vegetation,
- the current and projected impact of a species,
- accessibility to the site,
- complexity of effort,
- And, best management practice.

Therefore, if a species was only represented by a few individuals, but in time is likely to become a major management issue, it was assigned as a high priority species, and it was proposed that the species be eradicated. Conversely, if it was already widespread within the study area and intensive repeated management efforts were (in the long term) unlikely to impact on the species, and was not listed as a WoNS, it was deemed a lower priority and it was proposed that the species be contained, As from the data collected, multiple methods and strategies are planned to reduce or remove the weed threat from impacting on biodiversity outcomes.

4. Results

4.1. Vegetation Composition and Structure

The Werribee River, Surbiton Park study area supports three Ecological Vegetation Classes (EVC): Creekline Grassy Woodland (EVC 68 VVP), Floodplain Riparian Woodland (EVC 56 VVP) and Plains Woodland / Grassland Mosaic (EVC 693 VVP). From a bioregional conservation status all three EVC's are listed as Endangered.

4.2. Priority riparian weeds

Field assessments revealed a total of 35 environmental weeds that occur within and adjacent to the study area. The survey identified four (5) species of national significance (WoNS) and are also listed under the Victorian CaLP Act 1994, Chilean Needle grass (*Nassella neesiana*), Serrated Tussock (*Nassella trichotoma*) and Bridal Creeper (*Asparagus asparagoides*), have a very high risk level based on the level of impact, invasiveness, distribution and rate (and method) of dispersal within the study area. The majority of the remaining weeds are common and are regionally associated with Escarpments and Grasslands in the greater Melbourne area; several species found in the survey appeared to have been purposely planted.

The noxious and environmental weed species identified varied in their current distribution and density within the Park; however, they all impact on natural values and may affect the habitat of significant wildlife species through habitat degradation and elimination or reduction of food sources. Noxious and environmental weed species may also provide harbour to exotic predators and other pest animals.

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Given the extent of transforming environmental weeds that occupy the creek verge and escarpment, the preferred strategy would be to prioritise eradication and containment in areas of high quality vegetation and dense accessible occurrences, followed by suitable revegetation. Other exotic species such as incidental woody weeds could be feasibly eradicated from the study area.

Generally speaking, the majority of weeds are confined to the Park and are within the grasp of control. Transitional species are forging into quality habitat including areas outside the riparian corridor. With a well-considered approach, the aim of enabling quality vegetation and habitat to colonise the niche left due to weed control is an achievable goal

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Table 6: Extent of priority weed species recorded within Surbiton Park, Werribee River. 16th July 2013.

Species	Name	Status	Family	Life Form	Seed Bank	Source
<i>Aira caryophyllea subsp. caryophyllea</i>	Silvery Hair-grass	DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	POACEAE	Grass	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Arctotheca calendula</i>	Cape weed	DSE Environmental Weed - Medium Risk	ASTERACEAE	Flatweed	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Asparagus asparagoides</i>	Bridal Creeper	Weed of National Significance Regionally Restricted DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	ASPARAGACEA	Scrambler	Tuber	Garden escapee
<i>Avena barbata</i>	Bearded Oat	DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	POACEAE	Grass	Soil Stored	Agricultural
<i>Avena fatua</i>	Wild Oat	DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	POACEAE	Grass	Soil Stored	Garden escapee
<i>Cirsium vulgare</i>	Spear Thistle	DSE Environmental Weed - Medium Risk- Calp listed	ASTERACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Long term established possibly planted
<i>Cynara cardunculus subsp. flavescens</i>	Artichoke Thistle	DSE Environmental Weed - Moderate Risk- Calp listed	ASTERACEAE	Ground layer	Soil Stored	Garden escapee
<i>Diplotaxis tenuifolia</i>	Sand Rocket	CaLP Listed Regionally Restricted Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	BRASSICACEA	Annual	Soil Stored	Long term established possibly planted
<i>Ecballium elaterium</i>	Squirting Cucumber	Unprescribed Environmental Weed	CUCURBITACEAE	Ground cover	Soil Stored	Animal dispersed
<i>Echium plantagineum</i>	Patterson's curse	CaLP Listed Regionally Restricted Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	BORAGINACEAE	Annual	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Ehrharta longiflora</i>	Annual Veldt-grass	DSE Environmental Weed - High Risk	POACEAE	Grass	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Emex australis</i>	Spiny Emex	DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk- Calp listed	POLYGONACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Animal dispersed
<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i>	Caper Spurge	DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	EUPHORBIACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Garden escapee
<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Fennel	Weed of National Significance Regionally Restricted DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	APIACEAE	Annual	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source

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<i>Galenia pubescens</i>	Galenia	DSE Environmental Weed - Very High Risk	AIZOACEAE	Ground Cover	Soil Stored	Long term established possibly planted
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	St. John's wort	CaLP Listed Regionally Restricted DSE Environmental Weed - High Risk	CLUSIACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Hypochaeris radicata</i>	Flatweed	DSE Environmental Weed - Medium Risk	ASTERACEAE	Flatweed	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	Perennial Rye grass	DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	POACEAE	Grass	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Lycium ferocissimum</i>	African Box-thorn	Weed of National Significance CaLP Listed Regionally Restricted DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	SOLANACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Animal dispersed
<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	Horehound	DSE Environmental Weed - Very High Risk- Calp listed	LAMIACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Animal dispersed
<i>Nassella neesiana</i>	Chilean Needle grass	Weed of National Significance CaLP Listed Regionally Restricted DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	POACEAE	Grass	Soil Stored	Animal dispersed
<i>Nassella trichotoma</i>	Serrated Tussock	Weed of National Significance CaLP Listed Regionally Restricted DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	POACEAE	Grass	Soil Stored	Wind dispersed
<i>Opuntia spp</i>	Prickly Pear	Weed of National Significance CaLP Listed Regionally Restricted DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	CACTACEAE	Cactus	Soil Stored	fragment
<i>Phalaris aquatica</i>	Toowoomba Canary-grass	DSE Environmental Weed - Very High Risk	POACEAE	Grass	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Physalis viscosa</i>	Sticky Ground Cherry	DSE Environmental Weed - High Risk	SOLANACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Phytolacca octandra</i>	Red-ink Weed	DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	PHYTOLACCACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Pinus radiata</i>	Radiata Pine	DSE Environmental Weed - Very High Risk	PINACEAE	Tree	Soil Stored	Wind dispersed
<i>Schinus molle</i>	Pepper tree	DSE Environmental Weed - Very High Risk	ANACARDIACEAE	Tree	Soil Stored	Garden escapee
<i>Sonchus asper s.l.</i>	Rough Sow-thistle	DSE Environmental Weed - Medium Risk	ASTERACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Wind dispersed

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<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	Common Sow-thistle	DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk	ASTERACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	Wind dispersed
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	Unprescribed Environmental Weed	FABACEAE	Ground cover	Soil Stored	Animal dispersed
<i>Trifolium subterraneum</i>	Subterranean Clover	DSE Environmental Weed - Very High Risk	FABACEAE	Ground cover	Soil Stored	Animal dispersed
<i>Verbascum thapsus</i> <i>subsp. thapsus</i>	Great Mullein	DSE Environmental Weed - Lower Risk- Calp listed	SCROPHULARIACEAE	ground shrub	Soil Stored	garden escapee
<i>Vulpia bromoides</i>	Squirrel-tail Fescue	DSE Environmental Weed - High Risk	POACEAE	grass	Soil Stored	Established from upstream source
<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	Bathurst Burr	DSE Environmental Weed - Medium Risk- Calp listed	ASTERACEAE	Shrub	Soil Stored	animal dispersed

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Table 7: Summary of recommended strategies and priorities for weed species of Werribee River, Surbiton Park

Species	Name	Invasiveness	Impact	Strategy	Priority	Treatment
<i>Aira caryophyllea subsp. caryophyllea</i>	Silvery Hair-grass	Low	low	Contain	low	Spray
<i>Arctotheca calendula</i>	Cape weed	Medium	Medium	Contain	Medium	Spray
<i>Asparagus asparagoides</i>	Bridal Creeper	Very high	Very high	Eradicate	High	Spray / Dig
<i>Avena barbata</i>	Bearded Oat	Low	Low	Contain	Low	Spray
<i>Avena fatua</i>	Wild Oat	Low	Low	Contain	Low	Spray
<i>Cirsium vulgare</i>	Spear Thistle	Medium	Medium	Contain	low	Spray
<i>Cynara cardunculus subsp. flavescens</i>	Artichoke Thistle	Moderate	High	Eradicate	High	Spray
<i>Diplotaxis tenuifolia</i>	Sand Rocket	Low	Medium	Contain	Medium	Spray
<i>Ecballium elaterium</i>	Squirting Cucumber	Low	low	contain	Low	Spray
<i>Echium plantagineum</i>	Patterson's curse	Medium	High	Control	High	Spray
<i>Ehrharta longiflora</i>	Annual Veldt-grass	High	Medium	Contain	low	Spray
<i>Emex australis</i>	Spiny Emex	Low	Medium	Eradicate	Medium	Spray
<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i>	Caper Spurge	Low	Medium	Eradicate	Medium	Hand weed
<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Fennel	Very high	Very high	Control	Medium	Spray
<i>Galenia pubescens</i>	Galenia	Very high	High	Control	Medium	Spray

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<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	St. John's wort	Very high	High	Control	Medium	Spray
<i>Hypochaeris radicata</i>	Flatweed	Medium	low	Contain	low	Spray
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	Perennial Rye grass	Low	Medium	contain	Low	Spray
<i>Lycium ferocissimum</i>	African Box-thorn	Very high	Very high	Eradicate	High	Cut & Paint
<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	Horehound	Very high	High	Eradicate	Medium	Spray
<i>Nassella neesiana</i>	Chilean Needle grass	Very high	Very high	Eradicate	High	Spray
<i>Nassella trichotoma</i>	Serrated Tussock	Very high	Very high	Eradicate	High	Spray
<i>Opuntia spp</i>	Prickly Pear	Moderate	Very high	Eradicate	high	Stem inject / Spray
<i>Phalaris aquatica</i>	Toowoomba Canary-grass	Very high	High	Control	Medium	Spray
<i>Physalis viscosa</i>	Sticky Ground Cherry	High	High	Control	Medium	Spray
<i>Phytolacca octandra</i>	Red-ink Weed	Low	Medium	Contain	Medium	Spray
<i>Pinus radiata</i>	Radiata Pine	Very high	Medium	Eradicate	Medium	Ring Bark
<i>Schinus molle</i>	Pepper tree	Very high	High	Control	Medium	Stem inject
<i>Sonchus asper s.l.</i>	Rough Sow-thistle	Medium	Medium	Contain	low	Spray
<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	Common Sow-thistle	Low	low	Contain	low	Spray
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	Red Clover	Low	Low	contain	Low	Spray
<i>Trifolium subterraneum</i>	Subterranean Clover	Very high	Medium	Contain	low	Spray

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<i>Verbascum thapsus subsp. thapsus</i>	Great Mullein	Low	Medium	Control	High	Spray
<i>Vulpia bromoides</i>	Squirrel-tail Fescue	High	Medium	Contain	low	Spray
<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	Bathurst Burr	Medium	high	Eradicate	high	Spray
note: invasiveness and impact definitions from DSE Advisory list of environmental weeds of the Inlands Plains bioregions of Victoria 2009						
Priority: High- before next flowering stage, Medium- 1-2 years, Low- 3-5 years						

Interpretation of the field data determines some relationships with land use. Firstly, WoNS- listed African Box thorn (*Lycium ferocissimum*), is prevalent in all reaches, occupying areas of escarpment and embankment. Various management approaches are needed to eradicate and contain this species, with the strategy breakdown of three approaches in order of priority, namely:

1. Follow up control of already treated plants including recruits,
2. Eradication from high quality areas,
3. Targeting mature plants in marginal quality areas.

Two other prevalent species listed as WoNS for the study area, Chilean Needle grass (*Nassella neesiana*) and Serrated Tussock (*Nassella trichotoma*), are also to be targeted as a high priority for eradication. Although these species were not widespread across the study it would be achievable to control the species to a presence level.

Other species listed as WoNS are; Bridal Creeper (*Asparagus asparagoides*) exists in limited distribution over the site predominately under Peppercorns in Wallaby Gully, and Prickly Pear (*Opuntia stricta*) has a scattered occurrence but is quite rare.

Specific control methodologies and strategies for each environmental weed and its location are listed in Appendix 1

In association with Table 7 which shows the summary of recommended strategies and priorities for weed species of Werribee River, Table 8 outlines the degree of occurrence of all environmental weeds in comparison to all reaches. The information presented in Table 8 displays the species for priority action. Priority was determined on the need to feasibly eradicate those species from the study area that are simple to treat and where successful outcomes are expected.

5. Yearly Action Plan for monthly effort

Site	Priority	Botanical Name	Common Name	Jul-13	Aug-13	Sep-13	Oct-13	Nov-13	Dec-13	Jan-14	Feb-14	Mar-14	Apr-14	May-14	Jun-14	Method	
Wallaby Gully	High	<i>Asparagus asparagoides</i>	Bridal Creeper			1	1	1								Spray / Dig/ rust	
	High	<i>Cynara cardunculus subsp. flavescens</i>	Artichoke Thistle													Spray	
	High	<i>Echium plantagineum</i>	Patterson's curse		1											Spray	
	High	<i>Lycium ferocissimum</i>	African Box-thorn					1	1	1			1	1		Cut & Paint	
	High	<i>Nassella neesiana</i>	Chilean Needle grass				1	1	1							Spray	
	High	<i>Nassella trichotoma</i>	Serrated Tussock		1		1						1	1	1	Spray	
	high	<i>Opuntia spp</i>	Prickly Pear												1	Stem inject / Spray	
	High	<i>Verbascum thapsus subsp. thapsus</i>	Great Mullein								1					grub/slash	
	high	<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	Bathurst Burr													Spray	
	Mediu m	<i>Arctotheca calendula</i>	Cape weed													Spray	
	Mediu m	<i>Diplotaxis tenuifolia</i>	Sand Rocket													Spray	
	Mediu m	<i>Emex australis</i>	Spiny Emex												1	1	Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i>	Caper Spurge													1	Hand weed
	Mediu m	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Fennel						1								Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Galenia pubescens</i>	Galenia											1	1		Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	St. John's wort														Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	Horehound			1											Spray/ CP
	Mediu m	<i>Phalaris aquatica</i>	Toowoomba Canary-grass														Spray

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	Mediu m	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	St. John's wort				1												Spray	
	Mediu m	<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	Horehound			1													Spray/ CP	
	Mediu m	<i>Phalaris aquatica</i>	Toowoomba Canary-grass				1												Spray	
	Mediu m	<i>Physalis viscosa</i>	Sticky Ground Cherry																Spray	
	Mediu m	<i>Phytolacca octandra</i>	Red-ink Weed																Spray	
	Mediu m	<i>Schinus molle</i>	Pepper tree				1												Stem inject	
Stage 1 EFT days				9	1	3	3	1	1		0	0	1		0	0	0	0		
Site	Priority	Botanical Name	Common Name		Jul-13	Aug-13	Sep-13	Oct-13	Nov-13		Dec-13	Jan-14	Feb-14		Mar-14	Apr-14	May-14	Jun-14	Method	
Thistle Flat	High	<i>Asparagus asparagoides</i>	Bridal Creeper							Review / Report				Review / Report					Spray / Dig/ rust	
	High	<i>Cynara cardunculus subsp. flavescens</i>	Artichoke Thistle																Spray	
	High	<i>Echium plantagineum</i>	Patterson's curse																Spray	
	High	<i>Lycium ferocissimum</i>	African Box-thorn		1			1	1		1		1		1	1	1		Cut & Paint	
	High	<i>Nassella neesiana</i>	Chilean Needle grass																Spray	
	High	<i>Nassella trichotoma</i>	Serrated Tussock																Spray	
	high	<i>Opuntia spp</i>	Prickly Pear																Stem inject / Spray	
	High	<i>Verbascum thapsus subsp. thapsus</i>	Great Mullein																grub/slash	
	high	<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	Bathurst Burr																	Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Arctotheca calendula</i>	Cape weed																	Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Diploaxis tenuifolia</i>	Sand Rocket																	Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Emex australis</i>	Spiny Emex																	Spray

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Medium	Medium	<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i>	Caper Spurge															Hand weed	
	Medium	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Fennel															Spray	
	Medium	<i>Galenia pubescens</i>	Galenia															Spray	
	Medium	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	St. John's wort				1											Spray	
	Medium	<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	Horehound															Spray/ CP	
	Medium	<i>Phalaris aquatica</i>	Toowoomba Canary-grass	2		1	1											Spray	
	Medium	<i>Physalis viscosa</i>	Sticky Ground Cherry															Spray	
	Medium	<i>Phytolacca octandra</i>	Red-ink Weed															Spray	
	Medium	<i>Pinus radiata(single)</i>	Radiata Pine											4				Ring Bark	
	Medium	<i>Schinus molle</i>	Pepper tree															Stem inject	
	Medium	Revegetation with <i>Poa cells(after phalaris control)</i>						1										Stem inject	
High	Remove or repair reveg fence															2			
Thistle Flat EFT days				15	3	0	2	3	1		1	0	1		5	1	1	2	
Site	Priority	Botanical Name	Common Name		Jul-13	Aug-13	Sep-13	Oct-13	Nov-13		Dec-13	Jan-14	Feb-14		Mar-14	Apr-14	May-14	Jun-14	Method
Poa Slope	High	<i>Asparagus asparagoides</i>	Bridal Creeper							Review / Report				Review / Report					Spray / Dig/ rust
	High	<i>Cynara cardunculus subsp. flavescens</i>	Artichoke Thistle																Spray
	High	<i>Echium plantagineum</i>	Patterson's curse																Spray
	High	<i>Lycium ferocissimum</i>	African Box-thorn	1							1				1	1	1		Cut & Paint
	High	<i>Nassella neesiana</i>	Chilean Needle grass																Spray
	High	<i>Nassella trichotoma</i>	Serrated Tussock																Spray

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high	<i>Opuntia spp</i>	Prickly Pear													Stem inject / Spray		
High	<i>Verbascum thapsus subsp. thapsus</i>	Great Mullein													grub/slash		
high	<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	Bathurst Burr													Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Arctotheca calendula</i>	Cape weed													Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Diplotaxis tenuifolia</i>	Sand Rocket													Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Emex australis</i>	Spiny Emex													Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i>	Caper Spurge													Hand weed		
Mediu m	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Fennel													Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Galenia pubescens</i>	Galenia													Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	St. John's wort													Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	Horehound													Spray/ CP		
Mediu m	<i>Phalaris aquatica</i>	Toowoomba Canary-grass		1		1	1	1							Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Physalis viscosa</i>	Sticky Ground Cherry													Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Phytolacca octandra</i>	Red-ink Weed													Spray		
Mediu m	<i>Schinus molle</i>	Pepper tree													Stem inject		
mediu m	Reveg maintenance (guards replace)				1												
Poa Slope EFT days			8	2	1	1	1	1		1	0	0		1	1	1	0

Vegetation Management Plan: Werribee River, Surbiton Park

Site	Priority	Botanical Name	Common Name	Jul-13	Aug-13	Sep-13	Oct-13	Nov-13	Dec-13	Jan-14	Feb-14	Mar-14	Apr-14	May-14	Jun-14	Method
A Class Gully	High	<i>Asparagus asparagoides</i>	Bridal Creeper													Spray / Dig/ rust
	High	<i>Cynara cardunculus subsp. flavescens</i>	Artichoke Thistle													Spray
	High	<i>Echium plantagineum</i>	Patterson's curse													Spray
	High	<i>Lycium ferocissimum</i>	African Box-thorn	2						1	1		1		2	Cut & Paint/spray
	High	<i>Nassella neesiana</i>	Chilean Needle grass							1						Spray
	High	<i>Nassella trichotoma</i>	Serrated Tussock													Spray
	high	<i>Opuntia spp</i>	Prickly Pear													Stem inject / Spray
	High	<i>Verbascum thapsus subsp. thapsus</i>	Great Mullein							1	1					grub/slash
	high	<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	Bathurst Burr													Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Arctotheca calendula</i>	Cape weed													Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Diplotaxis tenuifolia</i>	Sand Rocket													Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Emex australis</i>	Spiny Emex													Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i>	Caper Spurge													Hand weed
	Mediu m	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Fennel													Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Galenia pubescens</i>	Galenia													Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	St. John's wort						1							Spray
	Mediu m	<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	Horehound							1	1					Spray/ CP
	Mediu m	<i>Phalaris aquatica</i>	Toowoomba Canary-grass													Spray
	Mediu	<i>Physalis viscosa</i>	Sticky Ground													Spray

Vegetation Management Plan: Werribee River, Surbiton Park

	m		Cherry																	
	Medium	<i>Phytolacca octandra</i>	Red-ink Weed															Spray		
	Medium	<i>Schinus molle</i>	Pepper tree															Stem inject		
A Class Gully EFT days				9	2	0	0	0	1		1	4	2		0	1	0	2		
Site	Priority	Botanical Name	Common Name		Jul-13	Aug-13	Sep-13	Oct-13	Nov-13		Dec-13	Jan-14	Feb-14		Mar-14	Apr-14	May-14	Jun-14	Method	
Stage 3	High	<i>Asparagus asparagoides</i>	Bridal Creeper							Review / Report				Review / Report					Spray / Dig/ rust	
	High	<i>Cynara cardunculus subsp. flavescens</i>	Artichoke Thistle																	Spray
	High	<i>Echium plantagineum</i>	Patterson's curse																	Spray
	High	<i>Lycium ferocissimum</i>	African Box-thorn												1	1	1			Cut & Paint
	High	<i>Nassella neesiana</i>	Chilean Needle grass								1									Spray
	High	<i>Nassella trichotoma</i>	Serrated Tussock										1							Spray
	high	<i>Opuntia spp</i>	Prickly Pear																	Stem inject / Spray
	High	<i>Verbascum thapsus subsp. thapsus</i>	Great Mullein									1								grub/slash
	high	<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	Bathurst Burr																	Spray
	Medium	<i>Arctotheca calendula</i>	Cape weed																	Spray
	Medium	<i>Diplotaxis tenuifolia</i>	Sand Rocket																	Spray
	Medium	<i>Emex australis</i>	Spiny Emex																	Spray
	Medium	<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i>	Caper Spurge																	Hand weed
	Medium	<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Fennel																	Spray
	Medium	<i>Galenia pubescens</i>	Galenia																	Spray
Medium	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	St. John's wort									1								Spray	

Vegetation Management Plan: Werribee River, Surbiton Park

	m																
	Mediu m	<i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	Horehound														
	Mediu m	<i>Phalaris aquatica</i>	Toowoomba Canary-grass														
	Mediu m	<i>Physalis viscosa</i>	Sticky Ground Cherry														
	Mediu m	<i>Phytolacca octandra</i>	Red-ink Weed														
	Mediu m	<i>Schinus molle</i>	Pepper tree														
Stage 3 EFT days				8	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	1	1	1	1	0

Total Monthly EFT

8																
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6. Summary of Reach Recommendations

- Wallaby Gully
 - Treat mature boxthorn.
 - Treat mature pepper corn.
 - Rope work required to get some weeds.
 - Bridal creeper to be treated.
- Stage 1
 - Remove tree guards from previous revegetation.
 - Retreat boxthorn.
 - Retreat peppercorns.
 - Stem inject mature peppercorns.
- Thistle flat.
 - Remove or repair fence around revegetation.
 - Stem Inject large pine.
 - Medium risks on slope.
 - Phalaris control a priority.
 - Opportunity for poa cell (grass) revegetation.
 - Retreat boxthorn and recruits.
 - Several Rubus parvifolia onsite (native).
 - Rope work required to treat some weeds.
- Poa Slope
 - Great native grass cover.
 - Mature boxthorn on top of escarpment to target (medium priority)
 - Phalaris is high priority.
- A Class Gully
 - Retreat boxthorn.
 - Spot spray Phalaris.
 - Patterson curse a high priority.
 - Slope work medium difficulty.
 - Spray large swaths of immature box thorn.
 - Treat large patches of horehound.
 - Fine rock work from top of escarpment required.
- Stage 3
 - Treat Great mullien.
 - Spot spray phalaris.
 - Retreat boxthorn and recruits.
 - Fine rock work required from top of escarpment.
 - Sheep impacting on tree guards priority to re set.

7. Occupational Health & Safety Considerations

Due to the nature of delivering weed control services on this particular site and other Western Water sites in general, there is a need for considerable investment of training and equipment to facilitate safe work delivery on escarpments and steep slopes.

The current effort of working on slopes has been set as a low priority due to inherent risks therefore utilising the current budget to focus on areas where benefit of effort can be gained efficiently with current resources.

Although in the short term this strategy can make demonstrable inroads to controlling weeds on the majority of the site, at some stage in time a concerted effort will need to be made to address the weeds on the escarpments to cease the source of seeds and propagules which continue to undermine the current and past investment of the wider weed control effort.

It is recommended that either; weed control budgets are increased to accommodate treatment of steep slopes or an annual project is run concurrently to control high priority weeds within the high risk areas.

Western Land Services has in the past provided this service to a few clients at various sites, however with the current situation at Surbiton Park the regular monthly budget would be exhausted treating the weeds with climbing gear at the expense of the other areas thus allowing the site to revert to a weedy state. It is therefore suggested that Western Water and Western Land Services work together to discuss options and to plan an achievable outcome that ultimately benefit Western Water assets.

8. Conclusion

At best, the current condition of Werribee River at Surbiton Park is very good due to the commitment and the efforts of Western Water and Western Land Services.

Weed infestations are for the most part confined to the escarpment areas; overall, with forward planning weed control and revegetation, the area can become resilient to climatic changes and further invasion by weeds.

The realistic intent from a practical perspective is that it is not the intention of this Management plan to maintain the site weed free; rather manage the site so to minimise the impact that weeds have on the quality of existing vegetation. The ultimate intention for the site is to arrive at a destination that is maintained to a baseline service level of effort that exemplifies sound land management practises and efficient use of all resources.

Transitional weed species have, in some areas taken a hold; this threatens the integrity of the higher value areas, and to a greater extent, impacts on areas outside of the Park. With commitment and a planned approach, this area can be restored to an asset of immense proportions in terms of linear habitat weaving through different land form, creating an example of harmony.